

K-pop's Transition to Online Concerts

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ABSTRACT

The concert industry went through a profound change in 2020 after the pandemic prompted live events to be canceled or postponed. The acceleration of livestreaming services grew within the entertainment industry and created a new wave for the concert business. This study analyzes two Korean entertainment companies, a well-established company, and a rising startup. It examines how both companies were affected by the pandemic and how they overcame the pause of live events worldwide. The research analyzes how each company operates online concerts and what they offer. The fan reaction to online concerts was also examined through social media posts. The aim is to increase knowledge regarding the surge of live online shows due to the pandemic and what issues resulted from the immediate adaptation to online events.

INTRODUCTION

Concerts have been live-streamed well before COVID-19. Music festivals, such as Coachella and Ultra, have live-streamed their week-long festivals, before the pandemic, for fans worldwide who could not participate in person. However, in 2020 nearly the entire concert industry moved to the virtual world. As the genre of K-pop began attracting international listeners, the Korean entertainment companies behind the phenomenon had to halt their global concerts due to the pandemic. Korean companies adapted to the new online world, and SM Entertainment was the first to offer live concerts through paid streaming services (Korea Times, 2020). Their live-streamed concerts surged during the pandemic, creating new live-streaming services, forms of performances, fan interactions, and some varied levels of audience satisfaction.

Korean pop was widely introduced in the U.S. when Psy's "Gangnam Style" became a hit in 2012. Before this, K-pop concerts were on a smaller scale in the States, but after Psy globally introduced Korean culture, the demand for K-pop concerts increased globally. The first K-pop concerts in America began in 2009, and in that year, there were only nine concerts, compared to 2019, in which there were over 103 K-pop concerts around the U.S. (Larsen, 2012). Nevertheless, in 2020 more than 60 K-pop shows, solely in America, were canceled or postponed from the pandemic. The cancellations resulted in Korean companies finding a way to safely bring concerts to all fans, which launched the online K-pop concert industry. K-pop has its own concert culture that involves stressful ticket queues, camping out, photocard trading, street fashion, and meeting the artists. This concert culture followed the move to the online world and created new ways for K-pop companies and artists to connect with international fans. This literature review will discuss K-pop online concerts, including K-pop popularity, online fan

interactions, illegal streaming, and innovative online meet and greets. This study will further advance online concert research by providing data about the transition towards online experiences throughout the pandemic and how companies accommodated them. As the K-pop concert culture continued growing and abruptly moved online, it is crucial to further understand how online concerts became the new standard in 2020 and 2021.

The History of K-pop

K-pop surged after President Roh Tae Woo lifted broadcast restraints that limited South Korea to have only two TV stations in the early '90s. The music industry took the lifted restraint to their advantage to establish new forms of entertainment and businesses. South Korea's culture rapidly grew in the 1990s with the increase of music, video games, television, and films that became popular worldwide. Its growth sparked the Korean Wave, also known as the Hallyu Wave, in 1997 and created significant changes to the global markets. Other Asian markets began researching the Korean Wave to see the significance of transcending many languages and cultures (Yoon, 2017, para. 2). Various entertainment forms such as variety shows make up a big part of the Korean Wave, allowing other countries to enjoy such shows as Running Man and Show! Music Core. It was not until the late '90s when the distribution of Korean entertainment had a spike across Asia after President Kim Dae-Jun lifted a 50-year ban that restricted the exchange of cultures between South Korea and Japan (Herskovitz, 1998). Electronics companies such as LG and Samsung also played a role in the Hallyu Wave. Both companies gained recognition around the '90s due to their quality and design, which increased their audience to a global market (Roll, 2020).

Along with various shows and electronics, K-pop is the most prominent form of entertainment that has helped South Korea distribute its culture internationally. Throughout the past five years, the K-pop market has seen exponential and parallel growth musically and economically. In 2004, K-pop contributed \$1.87 billion USD to South Korea's GDP, accounting for 0.2%. After K-pop rose internationally in 2018, K-pop began contributing more to South Korea's GDP, and in 2019, K-pop had a \$12.3 billion USD boost in Korea's GDP (Roll, 2020).

The "Big 3" music labels in South Korea (SM Entertainment, JYP Entertainment, and YG Entertainment) were the first to develop K-pop groups and are still active in the industry (Roche, 2019, para. 6). After many recognized K-pop's power internationally, people in the entertainment business began creating their own companies. Korean pop is a well-known genre internationally because many aspects contribute to making an all-rounder idol group. All-rounder idols are known in the industry to be good at every position required in a K-pop group and are recognized with the title of being an all-rounder. A K-pop group consists of having a leader, dancer, rapper, and vocalist, and they all complement each other as artists to create powerful music and performances. Members train for months or years until they have mastered the skill of being entertainers. Korean companies find success within K-pop because their music, visuals, and dance performances create practical cooperation that attracts different audiences.

The digital age contributes to the Korean wave, as it allows Korean entertainment companies to have access to sharing content across nations and allows K-pop to be accessible. Through an investigation based on K-pop and how fans interact, Yoon explains how Korean pop music and global media integrate fan engagement with artists (Yoon, 2014, para. 4). The visual arts of K-pop and their catchy music became a worldwide sensation. K-pop groups continuously gather millions of loyal fans that enjoy streaming the artists' content across diverse media forms. K-pop videos have broken various records on YouTube, such as becoming the most significant 24-hour debut garnering more than 74 million views (Tankovska, 2021, para. 1). The popularity of K-pop has only grown with the development of technology and music, as they all work hand in hand.

Korean pop music saw its breakthrough internationally in 2009 when Girls Generation (SNSD, their English abbreviation) released their hit "Gee" and became the "nation's girl group"

of South Korea (Benjamin, 2012, para. 4). The song's catchy lyrics, choreography, and fashion all contributed to the international popularization of the group. SNSD was one of the first Korean groups to break through into American media, as they were able to perform on various talk shows (Benjamin, 2012, para. 1). SNSD opened the doors for K-pop groups to break into the US market and was the highest-grossing girl group in the music industry in 2014. Still, it was not until 2017 when BTS (Bangtan Sonyeondan) marked the new movement for the K-pop industry in the west (MTV, 2018, para. 2). HYBE, previously known as Big Hit Entertainment, reached the same production level as the pioneers of K-pop as they backed boy group sensation BTS (SeoulSpace, 2021, para. 4).

BTS made its debut in 2013, beginning to grow in South Korea and internationally in 2016 with its title track "Blood, Sweat and Tears" (Herman, 2016, para. 5). Two days after the release of their music video, it had more than 7 million views due to the dedication of their fans, ARMY, who streamed the video multiple times. Since then, BTS has broken records and introduced K-pop to mainstream media worldwide. In America, BTS has become the first K-pop group to perform in the American Music Awards show, the first nominee for a Billboard Music Award, the first K-pop group to perform at the Grammys, and many more (Mendez, 2019, para. 26). BTS' breakthrough in America helped the K-pop industry to break through as well.

With the popularity of K-pop in America, Korean entertainment companies began hosting concerts outside of Asia. Although Korean artists performed in America before its mainstream reach, they opened for American artists. Once the Korean Wave reached the U.S., American fans demanded Korean artists and groups to tour America. K-pop is now widely known and has slowly entered American mainstream media by having radio plays. Throughout 2019, American and Korean artists released collaborations, such as Halsey, Steve Aoki, and Lauv featuring BTS,

to Blackpink collaborating with Dua Lipa and Lady Gaga (Kachroo, 2021). The K-pop and American Pop crossover opened the doors for K-pop groups to promote in America and caused K-pop groups to release English versions of their songs. As the demand for K-pop grew, K-pop concerts began increasing throughout the United States. In 2019, 30 K-pop groups and Korean soloists had tours and festivals with 200 stops across the United States (Frances, 2019). In 2010, there were only 18 K-pop concerts in the United States, and Wonder Girls accounted for 15 of those concerts (Benjamin, 2014).

The Surge of K-pop Based Entertainment Companies

After the Korean Wave arrived in America, live Korean entertainment had significant growth in demand. With the rise of popularity, the increase in entertainment companies advanced, and they all had one goal in mind, to introduce Korean artists and their culture around the world. The first convention that brought K-pop to other countries was inaugurated in 2012 and was in California (KCON, 2012). Koreaboo, a website sharing K-pop content in English, and CJ E&M, a Korean entertainment company, co-founded the convention (Koreaboo, 2014). They both created KCON USA, the most prominent way to bring Korean culture and entertainment to other countries. KCON USA continues to grow. KCON USA has hosted more than 24 conventions across four continents throughout its nine years (KCON, 2021). In 2019, KCON USA had a record-breaking number of 158,000 attendees for its two U.S. events in Los Angeles and New York (Asian Fusion, 2019). KCON USA is known for bringing the hottest Korean stars to Los Angeles. Whether it is idol groups, solo artists, or actors, they always have rising stars. KCON USA was only held once a year during the summer in America. Fans did not like waiting every summer and continued demanding their artists to tour, causing those previously in the

Korean entertainment industry to create live production companies directed towards K-pop and international fans.

As the moment K-pop rose, Korean entertainment companies based worldwide began surging. Companies such as SubKulture, Powerhouse Live, MyMusicTaste, and ATLocal started working with well-established entertainment companies to host concerts in America (Herman, 2018, para. 4). These small live entertainment companies worked alongside more established American entertainment companies, such as Live Nation, AXS, and Ticketmaster. The increase of K-pop concerts in America led Live Nation to open Live Nation K-pop, the promoter for K-pop events internationally in 2018 (Herman, 2018, para. 9). However, well-established K-pop companies began working directly with American entertainment companies to host their concerts instead of working with a third party.

The smaller entertainment companies depended on the demand for smaller K-pop groups to host concerts in America due to bigger K-pop groups having direct contact with American entertainment companies. MyMusicTaste is a South Korean-based company established in 2011 as a fan-initiated live event company (Crunchbase, 2021). They are known for hosting campaigns for artists worldwide, where fans aim to receive 50,000 petitions to bring the artist to their desired location (Shu, 2016, para. 9). Once fans obtain the signatures, MMT contacts the artist's company, managers and helps plan the tour. MyMusicTaste had worked for various K-pop groups such as SHINee, BTS, ATEEZ, and DAY6. All toured in Europe and America when they were less known. MMT gathered thousands of campaigns for K-pop groups worldwide during 2016 and hosted more than 50 concerts (MyMusicTaste, 2021). MMT had a bright future until the beginning of 2020, when many of its tours were postponed.

SubKulture, a Los Angeles-based company established in 2015, has worked with the same artists as MyMusicTaste, as they have collaborated on tours. Throughout the last four years, they have worked with up-and-coming artists or "rookies," as they are called in South Korea (SubKulture, 2021). SubKulture also has a relationship with fans, as they recruit volunteers from the artist's fanbase to help with publicity and volunteer at concerts. The recruited volunteers join a street team designated to the concert's location, where they help promote the concert on social media and in-person (SubKulture, 2016). SubKulture works directly with smaller entertainment companies based in South Korea due to their limited promotion of smaller venues outside of Asia, compared to what KCON can provide (Koreaboo, 2020). Powerhouse Live is based in Los Angeles, was established in 2008 and held their first concert the same year with Cho Yong Pil. They began promoting in America with smaller K-pop groups. Concurrently, they began working with AEG, an American entertainment company, which allowed them to promote bigger groups like MONSTA X, BTS, and Tomorrow X Together in 2019 (Powerhouse, 2021). Although Powerhouse Live collaborated with AEG to host K-pop concerts, they depended on group tours to South Korea (Powerhouse, 2021). ATLocal is another small company based in Atlanta, Georgia, created in 2018 after K-pop concerts became popular in America (ATLocalEnt, 2021). Being a newer entertainment company, ATLocal began working with lesser-known K-pop groups with a small audience in Asia and internationally, allowing them to only promote in small venues worldwide in 2018 (ATLocalEnt, 2021). Compared to Live Nation and AXS, the companies mentioned are smaller in scale. However, they are well-known companies for K-pop fans. Smaller companies that struggled to publicize and promote their concerts partnered with K-pop retailers to distribute free tickets to their events because of low ticket sales (Koreaboo, 2019). Entertainment companies have experienced a loss of profit before the pandemic in 2020.

Still, it is the first time the entire industry has been forced to adjust to a new form of entertainment.

MyMusicTaste, SubKulture, ATLocal, Powerhouse Live, and entertainment companies worldwide had to halt their live events for 2020 and find a new method to continue distributing entertainment. The common practice of these companies was to move to online livestreaming concerts to produce live content for fans worldwide.

Transition to Online Concerts

The transition to streaming live concerts was challenging for the entire concert industry. Artists started using social media more often to connect with their fans amidst the beginning of quarantine in March of 2020. Lizzo, for example, hosted meditations on Instagram live when much of the world stayed indoors (Mamo, 2020, para. 5). Diplo was one of the first artists to hold a livestream event where he performed a 90-minute set from the comfort of his home on March 17, 2020 (YouTube, 2020). When COVID-19 put concerts in America to a stop, many Korean entertainment companies, along with the rest of live entertainment, had to postpone or cancel their shows, leaving them with significant monetary losses (Brooks, 2020, para. 4). Due to the losses that companies faced through tough times, there was a need to quickly adapt and create new methods of holding concerts safely through the middle of the pandemic while also thinking of revenue.

SM Entertainment, one of the Big 3 Korean entertainment companies, was the first K-pop company to customize online paid concerts (Beyond LIVE, 2021). SM developed Beyond LIVE, which combines digital graphics with technology to bring artists and fans together via the internet. Beyond LIVE and SM held their first online concert in April of 2020 with their newest K-pop group SUPER M. The show garnered more than 75,000 paid viewers across 109

countries, estimating a profit of \$2 million from their virtual tickets (Herman, 2020, para. 3). Three months prior, SUPER M held a live concert at The Forum in Los Angeles, where they garnered a little over \$1 million profit, with an audience of almost 12,500 people (Billboard, 2020). Beyond LIVE has produced more than 13 concerts since April of 2020 for the most popular groups of SM Entertainment. Each online show was promising more than 100,000 attendees after SUPER- M introduced the new method of streamed concert entertainment (Kim, 2020, para. 6). JYP Entertainment became an investor for Beyond LIVE in August of 2020 to create Beyond LIVE Corporation (Bodegon, 2020, para. 2). The merger of both companies was formed to work on innovative technology to distribute live entertainment. It also allowed the artists of JYP to collaborate with the company to host online concerts. This transition to online shows saw fewer production costs than in-person concerts, leaving them with \$1 million to \$3 million profit per online concert (Bodegon, 2020, para. 2).

Like SM and JYP, BigHit Entertainment (HYBE) developed a live-streaming platform, KISWE. YG Entertainment and Universal Music Group later invested in the platform in February 2021 (Variety, 2021). They created KYBK Live to launch VenewLive, a live-stream platform that offers various forms of livestreaming concerts (Variety, 2021, para. 4). The three companies invested in the platform to evolve the performance opportunities and experiences for their artists and fans and became an established form of entertainment in the future. Big Hit's biggest K-pop group, BTS, held their first online concert in June of 2020. The show was streamed in over 107 countries and had more than 756,000 paid viewers (Cantor, 2020, para. 2). Normally an in-person tour would generate a profit of approximately \$20 million, yet this single concert generated the same profit (Millman, 2020, para. 2). In 2019, BTS' tour revenue was \$116.6 million, for 42 total stops in their tour (Frankenburg, 2019, para. 5). BTS would only

need to host five online concerts with the prospective paid viewers to have the similar revenue as their live tour with 42 stops. The merger was successful, as VenewLive grew revenue ten times more in 2020 compared to 2019 (Kiswe, 2021).

Although YG Entertainment invested in livestreaming services, they used YouTube and its membership services to host a concert for their biggest girl group, BLACKPINK. YG Entertainment charged \$30 for a two-month membership to the "BLACKPINK" YouTube Channel that gave access to the concert and exclusive behind-the-scenes videos for the subscription duration (Murphy, 2021, para. 8). BLACKPINK's online concert attracted more than 200,000 paid viewers, estimating revenue of \$10.5 million (TimesofIndia, 2021, para. 4). BLACKPINK currently holds the highest-grossing K-pop girl group tour, with a revenue of \$44 million from 31 shows worldwide (TouringData, 2021). The group would only need to host four online concerts to receive similar revenue from their live tour in 2019.

In 2020 KCON introduced KCON:TACT Summer, a weeklong online event, to replace their three-day, in-person event. KCON used the membership integration on YouTube to host its online events. Fans paid \$20 for a one-month subscription to the channel, where they had access to paid content, including the concerts (Benjamin, 2020, para. 4). KCON:TACT Summer had more than 30 K-pop artists and offered close to 600 different forms of paid content for members of the YouTube channel. The content was streamed 24/7 for the weeklong event and included live concerts, behind-the-scenes, meet and greets, influencer panels, and past concerts (KCON, 2021). KCON:TACT Summer received more than 4.8 million views across 152 countries; when it was live, they only visited six countries. Although KCON did not report how much they made from their new online event, it is likely that it has successfully transitioned to the online concert world. After KCON's first fully online event, they have continued to hold concerts every four to

five months. The transition to online concerts has allowed KCON to create streaming content for fans worldwide without stepping into their country (KCON, 2021).

MyMusicTaste has also become one of the companies that transitioned to the online concert community. MyMusicTaste continues to work with artists on a smaller scale than Big3 and KCON USA, and provides the resources to host online concerts. MMT has contributed to more than 23 online events for 17 K-pop artists during 2020 and 2021 which were live-streamed directly from their website, such as ATEEZ, LOONA, and ACE (MyMusicTaste, 2021). MyMusicTaste does not disclose any financial or attendee reports to the public. Therefore, the revenue and number of attendees are unknown. MMT and other smaller K-pop entertainment companies also focus on selling merch and hosting online fansigns, which take less effort to host and are very profitable.

Changes of Experience/Fan Interactions

Fansigns

In K-pop culture, the form of a meet & greet is known as a "fansign," where fans need to buy the artist's most recent album to enter a lottery to win a chance to meet the artist or group. Fansigns typically occur whenever an artist releases a new song or album. Fansigns are limited to 100 to 150 lucky fans, and they spend an hour in a venue with their favorite artists to meet them, have their album signed, and see special performances. This exclusivity convinces fans to purchase many albums, up to hundreds, to have the opportunity to meet their favorite K-pop group. The bigger a K-pop group is, the more albums a fan must purchase, making the fansign competition very tough and profitable (Soompi, 2016, para. 3). Fansigns were exclusively only held in South Korea and Japan on some occasions. It was not until recently, in 2019, when companies began including a fansign as a benefit for their international tours. MyMusicTaste

held their first fansign in the U.S. with the rising K-pop group ATEEZ as an add-on perk to their ticket. (Han, 2019). After their success with their first fansign, MyMusicTaste continued to implement this benefit with their other artists. MMT was the pioneer for holding fansigns outside of South Korea, with SubKulture initially collaborating with them in their fansigns and then branching off to create their own. After companies saw success with international fansigns, they no longer included them as concert ticket benefits and began to host them as separate events that forced fans to buy albums to join the lottery system.

After the transition to online concerts, entertainment companies rationalized providing benefits for their different ticket tiers. Entertainment companies also had to figure out how to hold fansigns safely to continue promoting artists' album sales. In March of 2020, K-pop group MCND announced their fansign event "MCND Meet & Call" through their Twitter account @MCNDOfficial_, the first online fansign. Fansigns have gone digital and are now accessible to anyone worldwide, further increasing album sales. Online fansigns still go through the same process of applying and selection, the fan has up to one minute with each member, and they receive a signed album along with exclusive merch for attending the event (Wong, 2020, para. 3). Every company has different methods of hosting its online calls. Many use Kakao Talk or Line, popular communication apps in Asia, or Skype and Zoom.

Smaller entertainment companies have had to focus more on online fansigns as their primary method of entertainment for the fans, as it is much easier to prepare and cost-effective. The companies do not disclose the revenue of holding fansigns. However, it is likely that the revenue generated versus the expenses paid is significant. Hosting fansigns is cheaper than livestreaming a concert. The company's only job is to run the event smoothly, host the artists, and have multiple phones, one per member of the group, to video call with the fans. Therefore

MyMusicTaste, SubKulture, and ATLocal have opted to host online fansigns for K-pop groups because it is doable for them compared to constantly hosting online concerts.

“Live” Audience

K-pop concerts are now accessible to fans worldwide, and it is easier for companies to host them. The accessibility for entertainment and the prospective companies is beneficial, but it is only helpful to fans to an extent. Online concerts are easier to attend, and fans do not have to worry about transportation or other necessities when attending a live show. Time zones are the only adjustment for fans during online concerts since they are streamed in Korea Standard Time. However, some K-pop fans are not content with online concerts because it is not the same experience as in-person concerts (Bell, 2020, para. 10). Tickets for online concerts range from \$30 to \$50, and although it is cheaper than a \$60 to \$400 ticket for a live show, the low prices are not always convincing. Korean entertainment companies have benefited from increased ticket sales by offering new enticements for fans. Innovative technology allows companies to highlight fans behind the artists on a big screen during the concert while the artist interacts with the fans and reads their comments (Wong, 2020). The live-chat feature on livestreams became the method for fans to cheer for the artist throughout the concert. VenewLive delivered more than 20 billion chat messages to the artists across the 13 concerts they held in 2020 (Kiswe, 2021). VenewLive had 1.4 million viewers that consumed 4.68 million hours of content and had 537.2 million engagements throughout the concerts. The average number of fans interacting per concert was 400 times per individual, including chatting, viewing the concert, and sending hearts or likes (Kiswe, 2021).

Interactive Merch

K-pop culture is vastly different from any other music culture, including its concert culture that is different from American concert culture. Many K-pop groups release the light stick that represents them and is used at their concerts or events as a way for fans to cheer them on. At shows, the light sticks are controlled by Bluetooth to create a magical environment for the artists and the fans with colorful lights. Owning a light stick is necessary when attending a live concert, and the entertainment companies understand how essential the item is during concerts. BigHit (HYBE) was the first company to use innovative technology to allow fans to connect their light stick to an app, allowing it to change colors based on the online performance (MagtheKpop, 2020). Other companies such as Beyond LIVE followed them and allowed fans to synchronize their light stick while viewing the livestream of the concert (KpopStarz, 2020). Exclusive merchandise from the concert has also been produced to be included with the benefits of attending the concert.

Nonetheless, if fans did not stream the concert, they can still purchase any merchandise. The new benefits created for online concerts have made many fans happy because it is still a form of attending concerts. However, others are not convinced and do not purchase tickets for online concerts for assorted reasons. Although pricing for online concerts is more affordable, many are unwilling to pay, especially while there is a pandemic. Fans believe paying for an online concert that is \$30 to \$50 is not proper due to unemployment some face during the pandemic (AllKpop, 2020). Fans have become resourceful and found other ways to watch online shows without paying, which has caused entertainment companies to lose revenue.

Illegal Streaming

The rise of live-streamed concerts in 2020 and 2021 is the new wave of entertainment for concertgoers due to the pandemic. Many fanatics are willing to pay to see an online concert in

the comfort of their own home, but some are not satisfied because it does not provide the same feeling as an in-person concert (Kail, 2021). In 2020, there was a spike in copyright notices due to people streaming copyrighted media for free. In December 2020, Congress passed three acts, the CASE Act, the Trademark Modernization Act, and a felony streaming proposal, protecting copyrighted content illegally streamed (Kelly, 2020, para. 2). The CASE Act protects artists who find their work being shared online and can be awarded up to \$30,000 to the copyright holder. The felony streaming proposal is specific to commercialized and for-profit content. The Trademark Modernization Act allows trademark owners to challenge false or inaccurate trademark claims (Mitchell, 2021). Congress implemented the new acts to protect artists and their content because of the spike in piracy streaming during the pandemic. The rise of piracy consumption costs the U.S. economy approximately \$29 billion (about \$89 per person in the U.S.) of revenue loss (Tillis, 2020, para. 5). Before December 2020, streaming pirated content was a misdemeanor, but the Protecting Lawful Streaming Act of 2020 increased criminal penalties due to rising piracy numbers (Supan, 2021, para. 7). The act was created to reduce the amount of illegal content being streamed.

Korean entertainment companies have faced various forms of illegal streaming before online concerts, such as the malicious streaming of concert DVDs and other paid content. However, online concerts only increased the number of unlawful consumerisms. Before COVID, entertainment companies worried about the streaming of in-person concerts. Venues worked along with the companies by prohibiting the recording of a concert because it consists of copyrighted content; however, it is hard to police when thousands of attendees are doing it (Gorgone, 2017, para. 4). In 2019, a fan was caught illegally streaming IU's live concert, and the police realized they had been unlawfully livestreaming IU's content for several years (Korean

Times, 2019, para. 4). With the transition to online concerts, the rise of illegal streaming became a worry for entertainment companies.

When SM Entertainment announced the first K-pop online concert, the company received backlash from fans outside Asia. Fans took to social media and trended the hashtag #SuperMDisbandParty to protest the prices of the tickets for an online concert (AllKpop, 2020). Fans were not happy with the \$30 ticket for an online show, especially with the crisis of many becoming unemployed because of the pandemic. Many fans who protested resorted to watching illegal streams of online concerts, stating that they would not spend \$30 for an online show during the tough times. SM Entertainment responded by announcing that they would take legal action against those streaming the concert illegally (AllKpop, 2020). BigHit Entertainment or HYBE experienced the same issues when their biggest group, BTS, held their online concert "Map of the Soul ON:E." The concert was illegally distributed in China through an app like YouTube known as Bilibili, and it exceeded over 20,000 unpaid viewers (AllKpop, 2020).

Entertainment companies caught on after their first online concerts and became stricter with the distribution of paid livestreamed content. VenewLive, owned by HYBE, included a Terms of Services section on their website explicitly explaining what will happen if someone distributes the paid content. They specifically added to the list that live transmission of the concerts was copyrighted, and if violated, the authorities will be informed (VenewLive, 2021). Other companies that hold online shows have similar terms of services and do not tolerate illegal streaming. After the online concerts became a norm for the entertainment companies, they began shutting down the livestreams during the show and have continued to do so.

Conclusion

Online concerts have taken over for 2020 through 2021 and allowed many artists to reach massive audiences through one event. Online shows seem promising after COVID-19 ends because entertainment companies and artists have realized the potential of online paid concerts. Compared to their tours, well-established artists and their companies saw similar numbers regarding ticket sales and attendees for one online show. With new forms of interactions with fans, the online concert world has created new ways for fans and artists to connect. However, this new form of entertainment can hinder those unwilling to pay for the content they are consuming (JoAnne, 2021). Illegal streaming is also done outside South Korea, and the action will only force entertainment companies to limit their streaming services due to the loss of revenue. Will online concerts continue to be a form of post-pandemic entertainment? Although online concerts are the new form of entertainment during a time of isolation, it is impossible to say that this will become a normalized entertainment method for the K-pop industry. This research paper will observe how two Korean entertainment companies transitioned to online concerts and implemented this new feature with their artists.

METHODOLOGY

Online Concert Observation and Comparison

The first method used was observing two live online concerts, and I took notes as I watched each show. The data was transferred to an Excel sheet that included in-depth information of ticket tiers/benefits, pricing, number of viewers, and the earnings of both concerts. Each corresponding online show is compared to the groups' most recent in-person concert to analyze the differences between online and in-person concerts. Two Korean entertainment companies were chosen by the scale of their artists and events to compare how they were affected by the pandemic. CONCERT A was hosted by HYBE, previously known as BigHit Entertainment, and they hosted a two-day concert for their most prominent artist, BTS. MyMusicTaste hosted CONCERT B, and they worked with Yuehua Entertainment to hold an online concert for their group EVERGLOW.

CONCERT A is BTS' "Muster SOWOOZOO," a two-day online concert held by VENEWLive on June 13-14 at 6 p.m. Korea Standard Time, or 2 a.m. Pacific Standard Time. Price of tickets ranged from \$45 to \$85, and each tier had a benefit that included the option of replaying the concert. The concert's duration was 2.5 hours, and it followed a similar structure to their in-person concerts. After observing the online concert, the data was transferred to an Excel sheet and compared to CONCERT C. CONCERT C is the Speak Yourself World Tour 2019, which was BTS' last in-person concert pre-pandemic. The same information was collected as CONCERT A, e.g., ticket tiers, prices, benefits, duration, and attendees. The "Speak Yourself World Tour 2019" had 20 dates, and ticket prices ranged from \$50 to \$310 and offered benefits per tier.

CONCERT B is EVERGLOW'S "The First" online concert held by MyMusicTaste on July 25th and began at 3 p.m. Korea Standard Time, or 11 p.m. Pacific Standard Time. Price of tickets ranged from \$35 to \$107 and offered seven tiers, each having different benefits for the viewer such as a shirt, exclusive photocards, a video call with the artist, and soundcheck. The concert's duration was approximately one hour and followed a similar setlist structure to their most recent in-person concert. Observations were taken in a Word document and were transferred to an Excel sheet to compare EVERGLOW's online concert to their most recent in-person concert. CONCERT D is EVERGLOW's in-person concert "Everlasting Tour" from 2020. Similar information was obtained from the in-person concert, such as shows, ticket tiers, prices, duration, and merchandise sold. The "Everlasting Tour" had five shows, but one concert was canceled due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The price of tickets for their in-person concert ranged from \$79 to \$170 and offered four tiers with numerous benefits, such as taking a photo with the artist and receiving exclusive merch. MyMusicTaste offered an additional package for \$149 that included a 40-minute meet and greet with the artists.

After observing BTS and EVERGLOW's online concerts, I transferred the observation notes to an Excel sheet. The Excel sheet consists of data that included ticket prices, number of attendees, and the description of how each online concert occurred. The same data was collected for two of the most recent in-person concerts BTS and EVERGLOW had pre-pandemic. The actual comparison of online to in-person concerts is presented in the results section of this research paper.

Tweet Collection

The second method was the collection of tweets published by fans sharing their thoughts about online concerts. The advanced search option on Twitter was used to collect publicly posted

tweets with the designated hashtag, date, and time per online concert, as they each had their hashtag. The hashtags used to find BTS fan interactions on Twitter were #BTSMuster, #BTSMuster2021, #BTSMusterSoWooZoo, #SOWOOZOO_D1, #SOWOOZOO_D2. To collect accurate tweets within the day and time of the online shows, the date was filtered from June 13 to June 14. For EVERGLOW's concert, similar data was collected with similar filters to collect publicly posted tweets of the fans' thoughts while watching the show and their impressions and reactions afterwards. The fans created hashtags for EVERGLOW's concert which were #EVERGLOW_THEFIRST and #TheFirst_Today. The date and time were filtered from July 25 to July 26 from 10 p.m. to 6 a.m., to accurately collect fans' tweets before, during, and after the concert. 200 tweets were collected in total and were categorized into eight themes. To protect the identities of the Twitter users and their usernames, they have been identified anonymously as Twitter users, BTS fans, or EVERGLOW fans.

RESULTS

Tweet Collection

After collecting 200 tweets for both online concerts using Twitter's advanced search tool, I sorted the tweets into eight categories. I created the categories based on the common themes found within each tweet. Both concerts had four similar themes, and the other four categories were based on the uniqueness of experiences. The common themes are analyzed with tweets from both BTS and EVERGLOW's fanbase. The most prominent theme found across both fanbases of BTS and EVERGLOW was the *Third-Party Stream Access Experience*, which consists of fans asking, sharing, and joking about the free streaming links for the online concerts. Below is an example of a tweet that a fan shared on Twitter after BTS' online concert ended:

“A biggest thanks to all the ppl who provided muster l!nks despite getting reported over and over. I hope you all get bts front row tickets. Thank you so much for helping us broke armys. We were able to watch it because of you”

The Twitter user shared how thankful they were for the fans who provided third-party streams to the online concert. The user also includes in their tweet how difficult their experience was to watch the stream for free since VenewLive was taking down the third-party streams. Armys are the name of the BTS fanbase, and some fans are willing to share a stream of the concert for free because they know some fans cannot afford it. The user typed links as “l!nks” to hide their tweet from being found if one searches “links.” Fans “code” their tweets with asterisks or numbers to replace letters, making it harder for their tweets to be found. During online concerts, this is usually done, so entertainment company employees have a more challenging time finding and reporting the links. Another method that fans use on Twitter to share the link secretly is that fans go on private, so only their followers can access the association. A Twitter user tweeted,

“if u want the link to the everglow concert imma post it 5 minutes before it starts and then go priv lmao”

The *Third-Party Stream Access Experience* varied depending on the group hosting an online concert. This was dependent on the demand of third-party streams, plus the bigger the K-pop group is, the easier it is to find a free stream.

The second theme was *Paid Streamer Satisfaction* where there was a commonality of BTS and EVERGLOW fans tweeting their thoughts about the concert after it ended. A majority of the positive posts about the concert were from paid viewers, including this tweet shared on their Twitter:

“I'm sleep deprived and but god it was so worth it. this concert was one of the best things I have ever spent money on, you can clearly see how hard Everglow worked to bring us amazing performances and they did Not disappoint!! I really hope we can meet in person soon”

The user included in their tweet how satisfied they were to have spent money on the online concert, even if they were sleep deprived. Fans are willing to spend money to support their favorite artists. Some fans began purchasing online livestream concert tickets after being a part of a third-party stream, but had a challenging time finding a stable free stream, as evidenced here:

“actually, bought the muster ticket for today after I jumped between 6 streams in the space of 30 mins yday. capitalism you win this round”

A BTS fan on Twitter shared how they struggled through six free streams and gave up after not finding a high-quality stream. Fans who previously experienced viewing concerts through free

streams slowly became paid viewers because they did not want to go through the struggle of finding a stream that is high quality and that will not get reported.

Viewing online concerts can be a hassle when there are technological issues, and it is out of the viewer's control. The time difference between the concert and ticket activation can confuse those who have never experienced attending an online concert. The third common theme between the two fanbases is *Paid Streamer Dissatisfaction*. A Twitter user shared their thoughts of EVERGLOW's online concert and their unpleasant experience:

“I paid money for this and it keeps freezing and it's NOT my internet. I lowered the resolution and it still freezes. WTF?!!! #EVERGLOW_THE_FIRST #EVERGLOW_CONCERT #EVERGLOW”

The quality of an online concert is one of the most significant factors for fans because it allows them to see their favorite artists as they have never seen before. Many fans pay for online concerts because they want to see the concert in its most optimal quality as compared to the third-party livestreams in a lower resolution. This Twitter user experienced their online concert stream lag and had a lower resolution, even though they specifically paid to not encounter these issues. Some paid streamers for the online concert shared their disappointment with other fans because of the third-party livestreaming. A BTS fan shared the link of third-party streams to report with their followers on Twitter:

"Armys!!!! Attention please. Please report this account. They are going to live the concert for free on YouTube and it's definitely illegal!! Report: [YouTube link] #BTSMusterSoWooZoo #BTSARMY #BTS #BTSFesta2021"

The tweet above shows how paid streamers are dissatisfied with fans streaming the concert for free. Many are willing to report the links to ensure they are taken down for copyright

infringement. However, it is impossible to control since there are hundreds of free streams available.

The fourth theme was *Repost of Content*, where fans requested the content to be reposted and shared for free, and fans shared the content via various platforms. The content reposted was made available for free, specifically for fans who missed the concert or because fans talked about the show and included screen recordings of the clips. Fans rely on other fans who repost the content and would rather wait for it instead of paying for the online ticket. There is a fan account that is well known across the BTS fandom for the reposts of all paid content. Such fan accounts are known for reposting content and garner thousands of viewers when they stream the online concerts via third-party apps. A Twitter user known for reposting content shared on Twitter to let fans know where they could access the recording of the online concert.

Fans reupload the content on different websites such as Google Drive, Daily Motion, and Discord to share the paid content to bypass the copyright infringement on social media platforms. Although the repost of online concert content is forbidden because of copyright, fans dismiss the agreement terms to help those who cannot afford to pay for the concert or those who missed the event.

The last common theme that fans experienced for both concerts was *Missing the Concert* for several reasons. Fans took to Twitter to share their unfortunate experiences on why they could not watch the online concert. Reasons include working, time zones, not buying tickets, and being tired of waiting for the online concert. A Twitter user shared their reason why they could not stream the online concert:

“LITERALLY SOBBING EVERYONE IS TALKING ABT THE EVERGLOW
CONCERT WHILE IM MAKING SANDWICHES FOR ANGRY
CUSTOMERS”

Although online concerts are more accessible, fans are still missing the experience because it is not within their availability since the time zone is based on Korea Standard Time. Fans who experience this rely on others to stream the free reposted content, and they also look for free streams:

“Really wish I could have afforded tickets to BTS’ Muster Sowoozoo huhu. And I also struggle with the time difference If there are any recorded links for the whole concert (which I know is already so tough to come by), pls help a broke baby ARMY out with links huhu.”

A Twitter user expressed how they cannot afford tickets and struggle with South Korea's time difference and location. They are one of many fans who continue to ask for the free content of the concert since they were unable to watch the paid livestream.

After reviewing the themes of the tweets made by fans, three outlier themes were formed based on limited discussion or because it was only specific to one concert. The only outlier theme found for EVERGLOW's concert was the *fan interactions* since fans did not share their thoughts on social media because it was not a big deal. EVERGLOW created a project where fans sent a voice recording of singing a song and it was included during the livestream of their performance.

A Twitter user shared their experience as fans who participated in the project:

"I think I hear my voice. Yes I participated in this event. I can't buy the ticket, so I contributed my voice to show support for the girls. #EVERGLOW
#EVERGLOW_THEFIRST #EVERGLOW_CONCERT @EVERGLOW_twt"

Fans who were unable to view the paid stream used fan projects to be a part of the concert one way or another. Few fans knew about the project or took part, so there is not enough discussion from fans on Twitter about this experience. The difference with online concerts is that fans cannot physically interact with the artist compared to in-person concerts. A chat box is available for fans to send messages to the artist throughout the concert to create a sense of interaction. EVERGLOW used this feature to interact with their fans during their breaks, and fans were ecstatic to have some form of interaction. An EVERGLOW fan took to Twitter and shared their thoughts on this interaction:

“Members are replying to specific comments in the chat so at least the address to the audience in between songs is probably not pre-recorded #EVERGLOW_The first”

Having live interaction with fans also removes the idea that the online concert is a pre-recording, which is another reason some fans do not pay for online concerts.

For BTS’ online concert, there were two outliers specifically on how fans reacted towards the concert and their methods of viewing the paid stream. The first outlier theme is *Account Sharing* between fans. Because VenewLive allows up to two devices to view the concert by only paying for one ticket, fans figured out they could split the price and watch from two devices. BTS fans used Twitter to find other fans interested in splitting the price and sharing their accounts to view the concert. A Twitter user posted a tweet to locate fans interested in sharing accounts:

“Still looking for a partner i can share or split the price for the ticket today kindly message me so i can purchase it now. #BTs #BTSFesta #BTSMusterSoWooZoo #BTSMuster”

The *Account Sharing* feature that VenewLive offered allowed many fans to afford the online concert because the \$45 ticket was \$22.50 per person if the account was shared. Another user also used Twitter to find another fan to split the price and share the account:

"I heard muster tickets can be shared on 2 accounts/devices. If any army has a slot available that they're willing to share please dm me I will be forever grateful
#BTS8thAnniversary #BTSMusterSoWooZoo #BTSARMY #BTS #BTSMuster
#BTSMuster2021"

Account Sharing has become a valuable feature for fans who cannot pay the total price for an online concert. VenewLive is the only livestreaming provider that offers this feature, and fans use it to their advantage.

The final theme found within the BTS fanbase is the *Purchase of Merchandise During the Concert* since BTS inspired fans to buy their items while watching the concert. Towards the end of the concert, BTS had an outfit change where they wore their merchandise from the concert, and fans began buying the items during the concert after seeing BTS wear it. A Twitter user shared on Twitter what they bought after seeing the BTS members wear the items:

“so, i impulsively bought that yoonjin mini bag and namjoon’s muster t shirt. . .
why am i like this”

After seeing the members wear their merchandise, the Twitter user bought what their favorite members wore. They mentioned they bought the yoonjin bag, as BTS members SUGA and JIN wore the bag from their concert merch. They also bought the t-shirt that BTS member RM wore. K-pop companies know that this is a successful tactic to persuade fans to buy other merchandise after the concert during in-person concerts. It continues to work in online shows.

DISCUSSION

Concert Observation and Comparison

BigHit Entertainment and VenewLive hosted the online concert “2021 Muster Sowoozoo” for BTS. The two-day online concert was announced on May 26th, and the sale began the same day and went on for three weeks. Four tiers were available for purchase, and each tier came with different benefits. The Single-View 1-day ticket was sold for \$45, and it included a replay of the concert and a one-day online ticket. The Single-View 2-day ticket was \$85, and it came with a replay of the concert and tickets to both days. Fans who bought Single View tickets could only see the online concert through one view. The other tiers were only available for fans who paid \$20 for the BTS fan club membership. The Multi-View 1-day ticket was \$45 and allowed the purchaser to replay the concert with the possibility of viewing the online concert from nine different points of view. The last tier available was the Multi-View 2-day ticket that came with access to the online concert for both days, the replay, and the nine different camera angles to view the concert. The Multi-View tiers were only available for those with a membership, and it featured seven solo cameras for each member of BTS plus two different views of the entire group. Fans with the membership were able to change views throughout the concert as part of their benefit of being in the fan club. A replay was available the day after each concert, and fans could only rewatch the concert once. BigHit Entertainment’s partnership with VenewLive allows fans to experience the multi-view choice.

The concert ticket prices for BTS’ in-person shows were sold for \$50 to \$350, with each ticket having its benefit. Ticket tiers from P5 to P6 or tickets from \$50 to \$215 received the same benefit, entry to the concert. As the prices increase, the closer the seats were to the stage. Those who paid \$250 for P7 received a silver soundcheck, which came with a lanyard, VIP Merch line,

soundcheck, and entry to the show. The most expensive ticket going for \$350 was a gold soundcheck with the same benefits as silver, except the seats were the closest to the stage. With the scarcity of tickets, these prices were only available during the general sale that sold out in less than ten minutes (Herman, 2019). With the popularity of BTS worldwide, scalpers — people who resell tickets for an inflated price — joined the world of K-pop and caused tickets to be unattainable because of their ridiculous resale value. Online concerts have made it accessible for fans to buy tickets without worrying about scarcity and resale value.

BTS' online concert followed a similar structure to their earlier in-person concerts. The duration of the online show was two hours and 30 minutes, which is the same duration as their in-person concerts. The structure of BTS' online show "Sowoozoo" was observed and compared to their previous in-person concert, "Speak Yourself," where they toured for five months across the United States. For the online concert, BTS performed 15 songs in total. They performed their most recent title tracks and special stages where each member performed their solo songs.

Compared to their in-person concerts, they performed 24 songs that included their title tracks, solo songs, and a medley of their older songs. To give the artists a breathing break in the online concert, four VCRs were placed every three songs, and at the in-person concert, it was placed after every eight songs. VCRs are short clips that K-pop artists show between their performances to give them 3 to 5 minutes to take a break and change their outfits. The VCRs are small skits of the artists or a montage to introduce the upcoming songs that the artist will perform.

Along with the VCRs, "ments" — a time when the artists take a break to give a short speech to the fans — were used for BTS to take the time to interact with the audience. For both concerts, BTS had four "ments" in total. However, the form of interaction was different. The

form of interaction for the online concert was through a chat box where fans sent their messages, and BTS would take five minutes to read them. This is a new form of interaction between the artist and fan because, during the in-person concerts, the form of fan and artist interaction consisted of the artists talking and sharing their thoughts and the fans listening. Fans did not face the language barrier in the online concert because everything was translated live as the members talked. At in-person concerts, it takes extra time for the “ments” because a translator translates after each member, whereas at the online concert, fans have the subtitles right in front of them in real-time.

Fan behavior at K-pop concerts can get extremely chaotic. Fans are willing to spend a week camping out to ensure they have the best seat at in-person concerts, but everyone has the best seat with online concerts. A form of fan interaction that was available during the online concert was connecting the fan light stick to the ARMY Bomb app, which is controlled via Bluetooth, and changes the color of the light stick based on the song that is being performed. The other form of interaction was through the chat box available during the concert. Fans could send comments to the artists, but it was not guaranteed that the artists would read them. BigHit Entertainment hosted a fan event before the concert at the in-person concerts where there were photo booths, merch booths, food trucks, and a resting station. Fans also created their trading station where they would trade fan-made goods. The most considerable fan experience during the concerts is the banner project, which is in collaboration with the fans and company of the artist, and they design a handheld banner. The banner has a message for the artist, and it is held out during a specific song that is chosen. Each tour stop has its banner design and own song, which makes it special to attend the show.

To compare how successful the online concert was for BTS, the number of attendees was noted and analyzed between their earlier tour and the online concert. The total number of attendees that BTS had on their tour of 20 shows was 981,525 (Rolli, 2019). This is compared to their two-day online concert, which had 1.33 million paid viewers (Basbas, 2021). Although their online concert had a difference of 348,475 more attendees, their earnings were less. The profits for the online concert were \$71 million, which includes ticket and merchandise earnings. BTS' revenues were \$115 million from ticket sales alone with their last tour (Rolli, 2019). EVERGLOW's online concert has no information on their attendee or earning records, as MyMusicTaste does not release that form of information for their online concerts. EVERGLOW's in-person concert had \$341,304 in earnings with tickets, merch, and their add-ons. Their earnings were based on four of the five concerts. Their earnings were cut short because of the cancellation of their last tour stop due to the pandemic, and they had to refund approximately one thousand tickets (Park, 2020).

Online concerts have two different perspectives based on the consumer and the business aspect. From the business side, online concerts can be financially successful for the artists and company. Through the observation of BTS' concerts, they were able to earn half of their tour earnings with only two online concerts. This is beneficial for the artist and entertainment companies because, financially, they are paying less for travel, workers, and other expenses. However, it can be both a benefit and a disadvantage from the fan's perspective. Online concerts benefit fans who are unable to attend in-person concerts because the artists do not tour in their country or state, it's cheaper, and the scarcity and resale value of tickets do not exist. Online concerts are a disadvantage to some fans who do not think paying to see the artist online is worth it. K-pop fans interacted with their artists online before the pandemic because they were situated

in various countries. In-person concerts are special to K-pop fans because they spend significant time with online media, and concerts are a way for fans to connect with the artist when they go on world tours. Online concerts defeat the purpose since fans are viewing the concert through a screen like nearly all the other media they consume from the artist. The interactions offered in online concerts are not convincing enough for some fans, so they rely on watching third-party streams to see the online concerts. Although online concerts are successful for artists and companies, the fans' opinion needs to be heard since they are the consumers and spend their money to see the artist or group.

Tweet Collection

After reviewing the 200 tweets and creating the themes, the fans' perspective provided opinions on how online concerts are received and what fans think of them as a new form of entertainment. After reviewing tweets from the *third-party streaming experience*, it is evident that many fans consume online concerts through this method. Although only 51 tweets were collected that mentioned such a method of viewing, it indicates how fans rely on third-party streaming to view the online concert. While collecting the tweets, there were threads — tweets with multiple replies — that included more than 20 different links to view the online concert for BTS. BTS fans used Twitter and the concert hashtags to find streaming links, and fans began relying on one enthusiastic fan account known for streaming. This Twitter fan account has a following of 754,000 fans. During the collection of tweets, fans mentioned how more than 500,000 people were viewing the concert through this account's free streaming service for BTS' online concert. The commonality between all users' tweets categorized in the *third-party streaming experience* theme is that they did not pay for online concerts because they knew there was free access to view the show. Watching the online concert through third-party streams came

with consequences, as fans had to move from stream to stream because the streams were taken down for copyright infringement. This led fans to spend more time finding another free working stream of the concert instead of viewing it through the original stream. Fans used various platforms to stream the online concert for free but were shut down due to copyright claims that the websites or platforms would recognize. The famous platforms fans used to stream online shows for free included Periscope, TikTok, Instagram, Twitch, YouTube, and Discord. After analyzing the tweets, a conclusion was made that these fans would rather struggle to find free links to online concerts than spend \$40 to \$80 for an online show.

Along with the third-party viewing, a similar theme was fans mentioning the repost of content after the online concert was over. Through the collection of tweets for this theme, many included Twitter threads or tweets with multiple replies featuring more than 20 links to rewatch the online concert. Although a benefit of the paid online concert was the replay of the online concerts, many fans wanted to rewatch it multiple times, causing them to record and share the videos online. Fans used various platforms to share the replay of the concert, such as YouTube, TikTok, Instagram, Google Drive, Dropbox, and Dailymotion.

Although many fans relied on third-party streaming for online concerts, a trend found in the *paid streamer satisfaction* theme was that many streamers paid for the online concert after initially being a part of the third-party stream experience group. The paid streamers were satisfied with paying for the online concert because they did not have to worry about finding a streaming link that would not be taken down due to copyright infringement. They were also willing to pay because the quality of the paid online concert allowed them to view the concert in 1080p compared to the third-party streams that had a quality of 720p or less (Venewlive.com, 2021). Paid streamers were also encouraged to purchase the online concert ticket because of the

multi-view viewing option. Along with the ticket, some tiers included unique and exclusive merchandise specifically for the online concerts.

After reviewing the tweets for *paid streamer satisfaction*, it was also crucial to see if any fans who paid were dissatisfied with the online concerts. The *paid streamer dissatisfaction* theme was recognized after a collection of tweets mentioned how difficult it was to access the online concert after paying. During the observation of the online concert, I had to pay for the online concert ticket, and it was unclear how to access the actual concert. A day before the show, MyMusicTaste sent an email with special instructions on accessing the online concert. There was a specific process to access the concert, as the concertgoer had to verify their name, email address, and enter the unique code given. For BigHit Entertainment, their only instructions were to sign in to the VenewLive or Weverse account that bought the ticket, and then the user was able to access the online concert through the app or website. The detailed instructions to access the online concert made it difficult for some fans to understand how to log in. Various fans also complained that the quality of the stream was low, or it would lag, and they specifically paid for the concert to not experience that.

Along with the *paid streamer dissatisfaction*, a common theme found was that fans tweeted about missing the concert and expressed their emotions. Fans missed the concert for distinct reasons, such as not knowing about the event, time zones, or being unavailable during that time. Since the concert was based on South Korea's time zone, the online concert for many in the U.S. was around midnight. The online concerts were not heavily advertised and would only be mentioned when announced a day or week before the concert. Because online concerts became normalized during the pandemic, fans started treating them like any other form of online entertainment they consume from the artist. This showed that online concerts could not replace

in-person concerts. It cannot be replaced because fans look forward to finally seeing their favorite artists in person, especially K-pop artists since they only visit America when on tour.

The collection of tweets also included three outlier categories since there were few tweets that mentioned *account sharing*, *fan interactions*, and *merchandise purchase*. These tweets were referencing the format of the online concert, specifically for BigHit Entertainment and their artist BTS. The partnership that BigHit has with VenewLive allows fans to be logged in to two devices with the same account. After fans found out about this, fans began to split the price of the online concerts and shared accounts. This caused fans to watch the concert for half the price, and fans used Twitter as an opportunity to find other fans who were willing to split the price and share accounts. The second outlier, *fan interaction*, was a common theme between both concerts since the artists only read the fans' comments for a brief period throughout the two-hour concert. The last outlier found through the tweet collection was the *purchase of merchandise* that only a few fans mentioned. The artist inspired fans that viewed the online concert to buy the clothing items they were wearing during the last half of the concert. This tactic is done in the K-pop industry during the last half of the concert. Artists perform wearing concert merchandise to promote the merchandise on sale. This tactic works because it is popular in K-pop fan culture to buy clothing items that the artists wear to show how big of a fan one is. The tweets' categorization formed a straightforward example of what the fans thought and experienced of online concerts.

Through the observation and comparison of the online concerts and the collection of the tweets, I asked whether online concerts would continue to be a form of entertainment post-pandemic. As the research on online concerts for this paper was happening, there were constant changes in the industry. In-person concerts began happening in America, and South Korea slowly followed a few months. It was not until November of 2021 when BTS was the first K-pop

group to host a concert in America, amidst a pandemic (DW News, 2021). During their first in-person concert in America in 2021, they implemented the new form of livestream entertainment for their concert, showing that they will continue to use this feature for their future concerts, as they saw how successful it was during the pandemic. BTS held four in-person concerts at the SoFi Stadium in Inglewood, California, where they performed their recent releases and songs that they were unable to perform at their concerts that were canceled because of the pandemic.

Along with the four shows, BigHit partnered with the YouTube Theater at SoFi stadium to livestream the concert for fans who could not get tickets to the in-person show. On the last day of their concert, BTS and BigHit also live streamed the concert for fans worldwide through their partnered app VenewLive. The revenue for the four in-person shows, four YouTube Theater livestreams, and the single livestream of the last show was \$61.6 million, totaling 813,141 tickets sold with the three events they offered attend the concert (TouringData, 2021). Half of the revenue, \$33.3 million, was earned via the 213,752 tickets sold for the four in-person shows at SoFi Stadium (Entertainment Desk, 2021). With the combination of the four in-person shows and the livestreams, BTS and BigHit gained half of the revenue they made with the 20 concerts from their last world tour. BigHit noticed the success online concert streaming has and will continue to implement this new feature for their artists' in-person concerts.

Although BigHit Entertainment has seen a successful transition to online concerts and merging in-person and online concerts into one, MyMusicTaste continues to host online concerts. Because MyMusicTaste works with smaller groups, they had a slower transition to in-person concerts. MyMusicTaste has collaborated with Jellyfish, a Korean music company, to host a nine-concert U.S. tour for K-pop group VeriVery (MyMusicTaste, 2021). The in-person concert benefits included attending the show and meeting the K-pop group. MyMusicTaste did

not implement the livestreaming service for VeriVery's tour and does not mention any plans of creating such implementations in the future.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

After analyzing the BigHit Entertainment and MyMusicTaste through their transition to online concerts and back to in-person events throughout 2021, each company's scale affects how they will host their events post-pandemic. The transition to online concerts is a current topic this year, and it is constantly changing. Future research for this topic may include distributing a survey, interviewing the marketing team of a Korean entertainment team, and seeing other companies hosting events post-pandemic. Due to time constraints, the survey that was going to be included in the methodology had to be put on hold because we could not reach a satisfactory population sample size. Future research can include a survey that asks qualitative and quantitative questions that can supply context on what fans think of online concerts and how they access the streams, whether via third-party streams or by buying an online ticket. Having an interview with a company representative would offer more insight into how companies view online concerts as a business aspect and understand how they measure the success of online concerts versus in-person concerts or tours. Because this research only focused on two companies, it would be interesting to see how other companies transitioned to online concerts and what they are doing post-pandemic. Since we are still amid a pandemic, future research can include how K-pop concerts will be hosted post-pandemic are and if there have been any changes made within the K-pop concert industry.

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